
Integrating Structural Biology

Instruct-ULTRA

WP3 - Expanding Instruct Membership and international outreach

Lead Beneficiary: P1- Instruct

Leader or Co-leaders: Susan Daenke (P1-Instruct) & Harald Schwalbe (P5-JWG)

Deliverable D3.3 Process for establishing joint activities with new countries and formalizing an agreement defining the shared programme.

Contractual delivery date: 31st March 2018

Actual delivery date:

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Project objective

To expand Instruct Membership to new countries, including international collaboration outside the EU.

D3.3 relates to Task 3.2 (Expanding international outreach) and Task 3.3 (Programme to establish new international agreements).

Executive summary

A spotlight meeting to discuss expanding Instruct membership and international partnerships was held on 8th March in Oxford as part of the General Assembly Meeting of Instruct-ULTRA. Two external speakers gave presentations on the structural biology communities in Austria and Brazil respectively, as case studies of potential new membership/partnership countries. This report from the meeting forms the basis of Deliverable 3.3 and sets out the next steps for expanding Instruct-ERIC membership in Europe and developing partnerships outside of Europe.

1. Introduction

A spotlight meeting on developing new membership and partnerships with Instruct-ERIC was convened at the Annual General Assembly of Instruct-ULTRA on March 8th 2018 in Oxford. Platform presentations were given on two case studies by invited speakers representing potential new membership/partnership countries. The speakers were asked to address four questions:

How active is the research community in integrated structural biology in your country?
What levels of organisation are in place in the research field of integrated structural biology?
What levels of interaction do you envision with INSTRUMENT?
Which levels of integration are required for the next years in your country?

The spotlight meeting was chaired by Prof. Harald Schwalbe (co-leader of Instruct-ULTRA WP3) and was attended by the Instruct-ULTRA General Assembly and Science Advisory Board.

2. Case study reports

3. Case study 1: Austria (presented by Kristina Djinovic-Caruogo, Max Perutz Laboratories, Vienna).

There are 14 Research Institutes/University Departments in Austria with molecular and structural biology interests distributed across five cities (Vienna, Graz, Salzburg, Innsbruck and Linz); the highest number being located in or near Vienna (Figure 1). Core facilities for protein technologies (including production and biophysical characterisation) and bio-molecular imaging (advanced optical microscopy and electron microscopy) are centrally provided by the Vienna Biocentre Core Facilities (VBCF; www.vbcf.ac.at) on the Biocentre campus, which is home to a number of Research Institutes, including the Max F. Perutz Laboratories (MFPL) and the Institute for Molecular Pathology (IMP). As an established service/technology provider, the VBCF would be well placed to offer access through Instruct. There is already cooperation between VBCF and CEITEC, which is part of the Instruct Czech Republic Centre.

There are coordinated investments in large scale instrumentation/facilities to be located in the Vienna area. Both MFPL and the Institute of Science and Technology (Vienna) have plans to each purchase a FEI Arctica and Titan Krios electron microscope which will benefit the community at a national level.

A doctoral school in Integrative Structural Biology (ISB) was set up in 2016 and funded by the Austrian Science Fund (FWF) that involves eight groups from Institutions located in Vienna. FWF funding requires that cooperating groups are in close proximity. There are plans to expand the scheme to new groups in the areas of cryo-Electron Microscopy and Mass Spectrometry. The groups involved in the ISB training programme could contribute relevant experience to Instruct for delivering courses at PhD or Masters level.

STRUCTURAL BIOLOGY GROUPS IN AUSTRIA - By Geography

Figure 1. Structural biology groups in Austria

Case study 2: Brazil (presented by Prof. Chuck Shaker Farah, University of São Paulo)

There are 17 Institutions in Brazil with facilities for structural biology including the crystallography beamline at the Centro Nacional de Pesquisa em Energia e Materiais (CNPEM) synchrotron (Campinas, São Paulo) and the 900 MHz High field NMR at the National Center for Nuclear Magnetic Resonance of Macromolecules (CNRMN) in the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro (UFRJ) (Figure 2). The highest number of structural biology groups (24 in total) are at the University of São Paulo (USP) and are distributed across three campuses: Institute of Physics at São Carlos Campus; Institutes of Chemistry, Biomedical Sciences, Biosciences and Physics at São Paulo Campus; and School of Pharmaceutical Sciences at Riberão Preto Campus). Scientific interests of the Sao Paulo structural biologists include drug design aimed at neglected tropical diseases, bacterial secretion and signalling systems, hormone receptors and novel lignocellulases.

There is significant investment in new instruments and facilities in Sao Paulo state with the construction of a 4th generation synchrotron at CNPEM due for completion in 2018/9 and the addition of a FEI Talos Arctica and a Titan Krios electron microscope to the Laboratório Nacional de Nanotecnologia (LNNano), also at CNPEM.

Figure 2 Structural biology groups in Brazil

There is strong track record of conferences, workshops and training courses in structural biology in Brazil, for example the Brazil School for Single Particle Cryo-Electron Microscopy – 7 schools since 2005 (next in 2018). Programs at the National (INCT), State (FAPESP CEPID) and University levels (e.g. Nucleos de Pesquisa-USP) have been funded to promote integrated projects that unite specialists from a variety of fields to study complex problems, for example CEPID Center for Innovation in Biodiversity and Drug Discovery (Glaucius Oliva, USP) 2013-2018.

Three institutes in Brazil (LNBio, USP Sao Carlos, CNRMN) are members of the Center for Structural Biology of MERCOSUR (CeBEM), a structural biology network that links nine major centres from Brazil, Argentina and Uruguay (www.cebem-lat.org) (Figure 3). The main aims of CeBEM are to integrate local capacities in the area of Structural Biology by fostering the training and exchange of students, the optimization of equipment usage, and the promotion and support of emerging small groups in the region.

Nodes in ARGENTINA-BRAZIL- PARAGUAY- URUGUAY-VENEZUELA

Figure 3. Participating nodes in CeBEM

3. Next steps

Europe: a focus on EU member states

The goal for establishing joint activities with other EU countries is to expand the membership of Instruct-ERIC with the ambition of recruiting four new member countries by the end of 2020. This is a challenging aim and requires that effort is carefully targeted. Historically, the countries involved in Instruct-ERIC were working together in prior structural biology alliances, for example SPINE, which led naturally to uniting together under the Instruct umbrella. Subsequent countries to join were most commonly spearheaded by a leading structural biology scientist, with the backing of the government ministry. Instruct-ERIC currently has nine EU member countries (Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Italy, Netherlands, Portugal, Slovakia and United Kingdom). Spain which has long-standing links with Instruct through the preparatory phase is likely to join Instruct-ERIC in the near future.

Austria is a newer potential member, and was chosen for the spotlight meeting as an example country with a mature structural biology community and a strong interest in joining Instruct-ERIC. Importantly, Austria has strong local advocacy for Instruct, and its national ERA Road Map published in 2016 has a stated objective to participate in ESFRI Roadmap research infrastructures. Discussions in Austria about Instruct-ERIC membership are now progressing internally to ministerial level.

For other countries the situation is less well understood. Defining a framework for establishing new links and developing existing ones is a helpful starting point (see D3.2). This is best achieved by a SWOT analysis, which we plan to schedule for Q3 2018, involving input from invited members of the ULTRA Exec and other strategic leaders within Instruct-ERIC. The various contacts which we have in new countries will form part of the analysis, in determining how well placed the contacts are to spearhead a national application. An important criteria is that there is cooperation between multiple institutes in any given country, rather than a single institute or research group who work independently.

We recognise two distinct entry points to the Instruct membership pathway, depending on whether the initiative came from a country ministry or scientist or from Instruct-ERIC highlighting the country after an analysis process (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Pathway to Instruct-ERIC membership for European countries

Instruct-ULTRA has resources allocated to work package 3, which can be used for travel to meet new contacts and for offering test access to scientists / institutes. Observer membership for Instruct-ERIC may be offered; there are not huge costs associated with this. If appropriate, fellowships to the biennial conference can be a useful way to draw new researchers or government ministry contacts into our community.

One final obvious place to start for expanding into Europe would be to convert Instruct-ULTRA partner beneficiaries into full Instruct-ERIC members. Greece and Germany are currently in the process of exploring membership.

Outside Europe: a focus on Latin American countries (Brazil, Argentina, Uruguay).

The goal for establishing joint activities with countries outside of Europe is to increase the international outreach of Instruct-ERIC with the ultimate prospect of recruiting member states as third part countries from outside of Europe. There are many geographical, economic and cultural hurdles to achieving such an ambitious aim. Within the scope of the Instruct-ULTRA project,

building productive scientific links in one geographical area would be a realistic step in developing an international profile for Instruct.

Therefore, the focus of Instruct-ULTRA's outreach outside of Europe has been Latin America where productive interactions have been initiated. Prior to achieving ERIC status, Instruct had co-sponsored with the Institute Pasteur and British council in Uruguay, a four day workshop (16th-19th February, 2016) on "Integrative methods in Structural Biology to enhance high impact research in health and disease" at the Institute Pasteur in Montevideo. One of the outcomes of this meeting was a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) setting out the context for future collaboration between Instruct and the Institute Pasteur in Montevideo. This has been used as a template for discussing similar links with other Institutes in Brazil and Argentina.

The status of MoUs (30/4/18) is summarised in Table 1. The aim is for the finalised MoUs with USP and the University of Montevideo to be signed following the Instruct-ERIC Council meeting in June.

Country	Institution	Status of MoU	Proposed/actual duration
Uruguay	Institute Pasteur (Montevideo)	MoU (signed 17/2/16)	5 years
Argentina	Leloir Institute, Buenos Aires	MoU (signed 1/3/16)	5 years
Argentina-Brazil-Uruguay	CeBEM	Draft MoU document exchanged	5 years
Brazil	University of São Paulo	Draft MoU document exchanged	5 years
Uruguay	Universidad de la Republica (Montevideo)	Draft MoU document exchanged	5 years

Table 1. Status of MoU with Latin American Institutes.

As a step in the direction of establishing a relationship above the level of individual institutions, Instruct-ERIC has also entered into discussion with CeBEM, the Structural Biology of Centre of MERCOSUR. CeBEM integrates nine major centres of the region, from Brazil, Argentina and Uruguay, that already have a strong profile in Structural Biology and Protein Science. The aim will be to engage with the structural biology community in Latin American with CeBEM acting as a point of contact and validator of potential partner institutions.

Preliminary discussions have been held with the following Institutions in Argentina; Universidad Nacional de La Plata (Buenos Aires), Instituto Leloir (Buenos Aires), Universidad Nacional de La

Plata (Buenos Aires) Instituto de Biología Molecular y Celular de Rosario and Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais in Brazil.

Building links with academic centres in Brazil, Argentina and Uruguay provides some general lessons for Instruct-ERIC in the development of international links outside Europe. The pre-conditions for a productive dialogue are:

1. An established structural biology community in the potential international partner.
2. Personal links to European scientists from Instruct member countries.
2. Scientific and/or technological interests of mutual interest and benefit.
3. Financial support for scientific exchange and willingness to travel.

The MoUs set out the terms for joint collaborative activities focused on three areas, namely access to services/technology, training and networking. The over-riding guiding principal will be the delivery of scientific excellence. The activities offered in collaboration will be subject to the same programme monitoring and review procedures as other activities offered by each party. It is proposed that a joint Training Committee is established with representatives of Instruct and the partner institution to oversee the planning and implementation of joint training courses. Draft MoUs have been sent to the Instruct ERIC-Council members for comment, with a view to executing the agreements at the next council meeting (20th June 2018).

Plans will be developed for organising a joint workshop and access visits. In this context Instruct-ULTRA will be supporting a project entitled "Expanding cryo Electron Microscopy to Latin America" that has been planned to reinforce access to cryo-EM for Latin American researchers. This project has been proposed jointly by the Instruct-ULTRA partners in Madrid (Jose M. Carazo, CNB-CSIC) and Oeiras (Margarida Archer, ITQB), in response to the Instruct-ULTRA Call 2 in work package 4 (reference D4.3) in the area of Internationalization of Instruct. It will involve a close collaboration with the Instruct-ERIC Centre and Instruct-ULTRA partner in Strasbourg (Dr. Bruno Klaholz, IGBMC).

Links for further information

University of Sao Paulo: for further information go to:

<http://www5.usp.br/english/?lang=en>

University of the Republic of Uruguay: for further information go to:

<https://www.fcien.edu.uy>

MERCOSUR Centre for Structural Biology (CeBEM): for further information go to

<http://www.cebem-lat.org/en/general/quienes/>